

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes/glassy carbon sensor for sensing of antiretroviral drug nevirapine in solubilized system[†]

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Abstract : A multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) modified sensor was used for the electrocatalytic quantification of nevirapine in solubilized system. The electrochemical characteristics of the MWCNTs film coated modified GCE towards nevirapine oxidation were investigated by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), square-wave and cyclic voltammetry. The results showed an efficient electrocatalytic activity at modified sensor for the electro-oxidation of nevirapine. The morphological characterization of multi-walled carbon nanotubes was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The multi-walled carbon nanotubes film coated glassy carbon electrode (MWCNTs/GCE) exhibits an efficient electron mediating behaviour together with well defined oxidation peaks of nevirapine. The potential utility of the constructed MWCNTs film coated modified GCE was demonstrated by applying them to the analytical quantification of nevirapine in solubilized system of sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS). Under the optimum conditions, the anodic peak current shows a linear relationship with nevirapine concentration in the range of 100–400 µg/mL with detection limit of 38.45 µg/mL.

Keywords : Nevirapine, multi-walled carbon nanotubes/glassy carbon (MWCNTs/GCE), voltammetry, solubilised system.

Introduction

Nevirapine [A], 1,1-dihydro-6*H*-dipyrido[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*e*] [1,4]diazepin-6-one is an antiretroviral drug (reverse transcriptase) and is used in the treatment of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) infections^{1,2}. Combination therapy has now become the standard line of treatment to manage acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS)³.

(A)

Nanomaterial based electrochemical sensors are of great interest in the new age electrochemistry^{4,5}. Cylindrical carbon molecules have novel properties that make them potentially useful in many applications in pharmaceutical analysis, electrochemical analysis, nanotechnology, op-

tics and other fields of material science. MWCNTs possess many special properties, such as high surface area, high electrical conductivity, chemical stability and high mechanical strength due to their special structure, unique properties and extensive applications⁶⁻⁸. MWCNTs exhibit remarkable electro-catalytic properties by enhancing the electrode conductivity and have the ability to promote electron transfer reactions, when used as an electrode material in electrochemical reactions between analyte and electrode surface⁹⁻¹¹. These effects are attributed to the larger available surface area of the modified electrodes which represents a new area of application for MWCNTs¹²⁻¹⁸.

The aggregates of surfactants, such as micelles, liquid crystalline, vesicles etc. which could enhance the stabilized content and the control release behaviour of drugs are widely studied as drug delivery systems. Surfactants heavily influence the electrochemical processes of electroactive species and thus are widely used in electroanalytical chemistry to improve the sensitivity and

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

selectivity^{19–28}. The goal of our work is to fabricate MWCNTs based sensor for quantification of nevirapine in pharmaceutical formulation, using enhancement effect of surfactant.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical behaviour of nevirapine at MWCNTs/GCE was studied by using cyclic voltammetry (CV) and square-wave voltammetry (SWV). In all electrochemical methods one well defined anodic peak was obtained, which is attributed to the oxidation of nevirapine.

Sensor characterization :

Surface morphology :

The morphology of MWCNTs was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using Philip SCI quanta 400 instrument. Fig. 1 shows the typical SEM image of surface covered with MWCNTs. The DMF dispersed MWCNTs film shows nanotubes twisted together. The average diameter of MWCNTs was observed approximately 200 nm.

Fig. 1. Scanning electron micrograph of MWCNTs/GCE.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy :

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) can be used as an effective and rapid method to measure the electron transfer properties of the electrode surface²⁹. Impedance measurements were performed using 1.0 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ containing 0.1 M KCl as a model redox probe (Fig. 2A). The electron transfer a property of two electrodes was also investigated using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. The obtained values of charge trans-

fer resistance are 14.2 k Ω and 4.4 k Ω at MWCNTs/GCE and GCE, respectively. The higher electrocatalytic activity and increased electron transfer rate of MWCNTs/GCE was confirmed by the reduction of charge transfer resistance.

Effective surface area :

Cyclic voltammetric experiments were carried out in presence of 1.0 mM $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ containing 0.1 M KCl to calculate the effective surface area of the two electrodes (Fig. 2B). The effective surface area of the fabricated electrode was calculated by using Randles-Savcik equation³⁰,

$$i_p = (2.69 \times 10^5) ACD^{1/2}n^{3/2} \nu^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where A is the electroactive surface area of the working electrode, C is the concentration of substrate, n is the number of electrons, $n = 1$ for $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ and D is the diffusion coefficient, D of $\text{K}_3[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$ is $7.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ ³¹. The calculated surface area for bare GC and $\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_3/\text{GCE}$ were 0.033 cm^2 and 0.049 cm^2 respectively. The results show increase in electro-active surface area of MWCNTs/GCE after modification which may be the possible reason for increase in conductivity.

Optimization of experimental parameters :

Effect of pH :

For controlling pH, various buffers such as Britton Robinson (B.R.), phosphate and acetate buffers were used. The best results with respect to sensitivity with sharper response were obtained with B.R. buffer. Thus studies were made in the pH range 2.0–10.0 in B.R. buffer at a target concentration of 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ aqueous nevirapine solution. As shown in Fig. 3, the peak current reaches a maximum at pH 10. Therefore, pH 10 was chosen as the optimum for rest of the study.

Effect of volume of MWCNTs suspension :

The effect of varying volume of MWCNTs suspension in DMF for fabrication of GCE in the range 4.0–12.0 μL was studied. Fig. 4 shows that the use of increasing MWCNTs volume is associated with an increase in oxidation peak current up to 10 μL and after that peak current decreases inversely. This is related to the thickness of the film. If the film is too thin, the amount of nevirapine adsorbed is low, resulting in a low peak current. When it is too thick, the film conductivity gets reduced, resistivity increased and also the film become un-

Fig. 2. [A] Nyquist plots obtained at GCE (curve blue) and at MWCNTs/GCE (curve red) in 1 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$. Inset : equivalent circuit used to fit the impedance data. [B] Cyclic voltammograms of 1 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, blank (curve a), at bare GCE (curve b) and at MWCNTs/GCE (curve c).

Fig. 3. Effect of pH on square-wave peak current for 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ nevirapine in B.R. buffer.

Fig. 4. Effect of volume of MWCNTs suspension on square-wave peak current response of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ nevirapine.

stable as MWCNTs could leave off the electrode surface. Thus, it resists the active surface of modified electrode and hence the peak current response decreases. Therefore 10 μL MWCNTs volume was chosen as optimum in the present study.

Comparison of square-wave voltammetric behaviour of nevirapine in presence and absence of surfactants :

The influence of different types of surfactants such as cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS), Tween-20 and Tween-40 on

voltammetric behaviour of nevirapine was investigated. It is observed that there is a substantial increase in peak current and the limit of detection is also found to be lower in anionic surfactant SLS while cationic and neutral surfactants showed an opposite effect (Table 1).

Table 1. Voltammetric characteristics for the oxidation of nevirapine (200 µg/mL) in different solubilized media

Nevirapine, B.R. buffer, pH 10	i (µA)	E (V)
Methanol	0.26	0.85
Tween-20 (0.1%)	0.14	0.79
Tween-40 (0.1%)	0.37	0.82
SLS (0.1%)	3.91	0.72
CTAB (0.1%)	0.27	0.86

The enhancement in oxidation peak current of nevirapine is related to the concentration of SLS. The relationship between the oxidation peak current and SLS concentration is shown in Fig. 5. Gradual increment in the peak current is observed as the SLS concentration was increased from 0.001 to 1.0%. However, the oxidation peak current decreases as the concentration of SLS

Fig. 5. Effect of SLS concentration on square-wave peak current response of 200 µg/mL nevirapine.

exceeded the 1.0%. The decrease in peak current response with increase in the SLS concentration is due to micelle formation, resulting in partition of the drug between the aqueous phase and micelle, i.e. it get entrapped in the insulated hydrophobic environment of the micelle and then diffused along with the micelle, which lead to drop in peak current. Therefore, 1.0% concentration of SLS was chosen for present study.

Comparative study of nevirapine oxidation at bare GCE and MWCNTs/GCE :

The electrochemical behaviour of 200 µg/mL nevirapine at bare GCE and MWCNTs/GCE was compared by square-wave and cyclic voltammetry (Fig. 5).

Under optimized conditions, there is a significant enhancement in peak current from about 0.51 µA to 1.02 µA in case of CV and from about 2.89 µA to 5.50 µA in case of SWV after the fabrication. The investigations showed that oxidation peak current at MWCNTs/GCE is about 200% and 190% greater than bare GCE. The increase in oxidation peak current is due to the increased effective surface area of the modified electrode. The higher value of oxidation peak current verifies the improved reactivity of nevirapine with greater conductivity after the fabrication of the GCE surface by a thin film of MWCNTs.

Calibration curve and limit of detection :

Square-wave voltammetry (SWV) was carried out with various concentrations of the nevirapine at MWCNTs film coated modified GCE. The square-wave peak current shows a linear relationship with nevirapine concentration (Fig. 7B). A series of square-wave voltammograms in the range of 100–320 µg/mL are shown in Fig. 7A. The peak current increased linearly with the nevirapine concentration and regression equation can be expressed as

$$\text{SWV}; i_{pa} = 0.027 (\text{NEV } \mu\text{g}) - 0.317; \\ r^2 = 0.9940 (n = 3) \quad (2)$$

where i_{pa} is anodic peak current in µA and n is the number of experiments. The calculated limit of detection (LOD) ($3\sigma/s$, where σ is the standard deviation of the intercept and s is the slope of the calibration curve) for nevirapine is 35.22 µg/mL. The low detection limit was observed due to enhancement effect of anionic surfactant SLS and electro-catalytic activity of MWCNTs film.

Stability of nevirapine stock solution :

In this study, nevirapine stock solutions were kept in the refrigerator at 2–8 °C for 20 days and were analyzed at different times of interval (every day). It has been seen that the peak current of nevirapine stock solution was stable up to 15 days and after that the peak current decreased. Therefore, nevirapine stock solution was found to be stable for 15 days.

Stability of MWCNTs/GCE :

The electrode stability of MWCNTs film coated GCE experiment was performed. However, MWCNTs film coated modified GCE showed variation in response after 3 days of its preparation and thus it is recommended that it should not be used for a longer time and a new elec-

Fig. 6. Electrocatalytic effect of MWCNTs/GCE sensor towards the oxidation of nevirapine. [A] Cyclic voltammograms, blank (curve a), at bare GCE (curve b) and at MWCNTs/GCE sensor (curve c). [B] Square-wave voltammograms, blank (curve a), at bare GCE (curve b) and at MWCNTs/GCE sensor (curve c).

Fig. 7. (A) Linearity of square-wave voltammetric peak current of nevirapine of different concentrations at MWCNTs film coated GCE in 1.0% SLS (pH 10); (a) Blank, (b) 100 µg/mL, (c) 125 µg/mL, (d) 160 µg/mL, (e) 200 µg/mL, (f) 260 µg/mL and (g) 320 µg/mL. [B] Plot of current vs different concentrations of nevirapine.

trode is to be prepared after 3 days. Experimental results indicated that current responses deviated intra-day by 1.41% and inter-day by 3.52% for first three days. Thereafter, the peak current response started decreasing.

Ruggedness :

The ruggedness test of the analytical assay method is defined as degree of reproducibility of results obtained

by the successful applications overtime and multiple analysts. Two analysts analyzed the same drug standard solution with same SWV method using the same instrument and parameters. The method was found to be rugged with the results of variation coefficient 1.68%. The results show no statistical differences between different analysts and time.

Analytical application :

In order to evaluate the validity, the above voltammetric procedure was successfully applied for the determination of nevirapine in its pharmaceutical formulation. A linear relationship between peak current and nevirapine concentration was observed in the concentration range 100–320 µg/mL in 1% SLS at MWCNTs/GCE. The current is mainly adsorption controlled and proportional to the concentration over a convenient range. The developed method showed good ability to quantify nevirapine in its pharmaceutical formulation with reliable accuracy.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Nevirapine (99% purity) was obtained from Veeda Clinical Research, Ahmedabad (India) and was used as received. Tablets containing nevirapine (*nevimune*) labeled 200 mg was obtained from commercial sources. NaOH (1 M) solution was prepared in double distilled water and used as supporting electrolyte. A stock solution of

nevirapine was prepared separately in methanol, ethanol, *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), 1,4-dioxane, water, cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) and Tween-20. All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade quality and were employed without further purification.

Instrumentation :

Electrochemical measurements were performed using a μ AUTOLAB TYPE III (Eco-Chemie B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands) potentiostat-galvanostat with 757VA computrace software. The utilized electrodes were MWCNTs/GCE as working electrode, Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) as reference electrode and a platinum wire as auxiliary electrode. All the solutions examined by electrochemical techniques were purged for 10 min with purified nitrogen gas. All pH-metric measurements were made on a Decibel DB-1011 digital pH meter fitted with a glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as reference, which was previously standardized with buffers of known pH.

Fabrication of MWCNTs/GCE :

Prior to fabrication, GCE was polished with a fine emery paper and chamois leather soaked with an Al₂O₃ (0.3–0.05 μ m) slurry, and then rinsed thoroughly with distilled water and methanol for few minutes, respectively. Then GCE was fabricated with a film by dropping a few microlitres of MWCNTs suspension in *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) onto the GCE and air dried. The experiments showed that there was an optimal electrochemical response for a certain amount of MWCNTs suspension. Below the optimal value the current became insignificant, and above that the resistance of films increased and the peak is drawn out. Thus an optimum concentration of MWCNTs suspension was chosen for fabrication of sensor.

Conclusion

In this work, electrochemical behaviour of nevirapine in solubilised system was studied using highly sensitive MWCNTs/GCE sensor. It is observed that the fabricated sensor facilitated the detection of nevirapine with good sensitivity and reproducibility compared to bare GCE or other instrumental methods. MWCNTs showed excellent electrocatalytic activity for nevirapine oxidation, showing enhancement of the peak current, which was probably due to the larger effective surface area and the stron-

ger adsorption ability of MWCNTs/GCE. The presence of anionic surfactant SLS also shows an enhancement effect in oxidation peak current due to micelle effect. The combined effect of electrocatalytic MWCNTs and solubilised system further lowers down the detection limit of nevirapine. Results show that the proposed method is accurate and it can be used for routine analysis of nevirapine.

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